

1 Recovering sand and gravel from End-of-Life concrete: The 2 global potential

3 Authors: Marc van der Meide¹, Mingming Hu¹, Bernhard Steubing¹, Arnold Tukker¹

4 Affiliations: ¹ Institute of Environmental Sciences, Leiden University, The Netherlands

5 Corresponding Author: Marc van der Meide: m.t.van.der.meide@cml.leidenuniv.nl

6 Keywords: Sand scarcity, Concrete, Recycling, Prospective Life Cycle Assessment, Stock model

7

8 Abstract

9 Concrete is a key material in our modern society and will remain an important material in the coming
10 decades globally. Two main components of concrete, sand and gravel -together aggregates- could
11 become scarce which may pose a significant problem the production of concrete. One option to mitigate
12 scarcity is to recycle concrete. Two complementary technologies that have been in development for this
13 are making this feasible; 'Advanced Dry Recovery' and 'Heating Air classification System'. Together they
14 produce recycled sand and gravel. In this study we assess the recyclability of End of Life concrete up to
15 2050 in 26 regions for the production of new aggregates with a dynamic material flow analysis model
16 and assess environmental impacts with Prospective Life Cycle Assessment. We find that recycling could
17 reduce demand for conventional sand by 16% and gravel by 34% globally by 2050 without large increases
18 in impacts, though impacts differ substantially per region.

19

20 List of Abbreviations

ADR	Advanced Dry Recovery
EoL	End of Life
HAS	Heated Air classification System
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
SI	Supplementary Information

21

22 1. Introduction

23 Concrete is a key material in our modern society and will remain an important material in the coming
24 decades globally. It is an engineered material mainly made from sand, gravel, water, and cement.
25 Production of concrete has quadrupled between 1990 and 2020 (Watari et al., 2023). Additionally, demand
26 for concrete is expected to keep rising in most world regions up to 2050, either for new construction,
27 maintenance and replacement of demolished buildings (Deetman et al., 2020; Sverdrup et al., 2017). Two
28 ingredients of concrete -sand and gravel (together aggregates)- made up 79% of all non-water
29 resources extracted from nature in 2010 (Krausmann et al., 2017). The winning of aggregates causes
30 land use change and hence may have biodiversity impacts. While the winning of aggregates is not
31 carbon-intensive, the production of concrete is highly energy intensive and was responsible for 3.3 GT
32 CO₂eq. emissions in 2020 (Müller et al., 2024). Their large scale consumption makes it important to
33 investigate how environmental challenges related to the use of aggregates could be limited (van der
34 Meide et al., 2022).

35 Although sand and gravel seem to be abundantly available, the scarcity issue of conventionally produced
36 aggregates has gained more scientific attention recently -though concern for sand scarcity is hardly
37 new, see e.g. Giljum et al (2000)-. Torres et al. (2017) have shown that illegal sand mining is causing
38 local problems in the global south. Peduzzi (2014) highlights effects on biodiversity, land loss and erosion,
39 water supply and potential damage to infrastructure. This poses a special concern to future concrete
40 manufacturing, which demands not only a high quantity but also a high quality of aggregates, namely,
41 construction grade sand and construction grade gravel. While construction sand is mostly discussed in
42 the scarcity context, construction gravel can also be considered scarce, depending on the region and
43 supply (Ioannidou et al., 2017), though the locality of scarceness is important for all aggregates. We can
44 expect these problems to exacerbate significantly due to the growth in demand (Watari et al., 2023).

45 Several options have been proposed to mitigate the scarcity challenge for conventional aggregates,
46 such as recycling secondary aggregates from end of life (EoL) concrete (Tukker et al., 2023; C. Zhang et
47 al., 2022) and increasing efficiency in material use (Cao & Masanet, 2022). Zhong et al. (2022) show that
48 to combat sand scarcity substitution is the single most effective strategy. The substantial flows of future
49 EoL concrete projected by Deetman et al. (2020) indicate a potential worth to investigate for sand and
50 gravel substitution by recycling secondary aggregates from the rising future EoL concrete flows.

51 While recycling concrete into construction grade aggregates has been an engineering and economic
52 challenge (Ren et al., 2021; Y. Zhang et al., 2019), two complementary technologies that have been in
53 development in Europe over the past decade are making this feasible. They are 'Advanced Dry Recovery'
54 (ADR) (Lotfi et al., 2017) and 'Heating Air classification System' (HAS) (Gebremariam et al., 2020). ADR
55 works by separating concrete pieces into different sizes through a mechanical system. The output
56 streams are recycled gravel and an intermediate. HAS works by separating the intermediate stream into
57 two smaller streams through a thermal system. The output streams are recycled sand and a fine dust
58 that can be used as a cement filler. The technologies could be deployed in tandem to recycle EoL
59 concrete and reduce demand for conventional aggregates.

60 For ADR and HAS, some work has already been done to assess their environmental impacts with Life
61 Cycle Assessment (LCA). Zhang et al. (2023) studied the environmental performance of the technologies,
62 including a prospective study where the energy supply to the technologies was adjusted to future
63 energy mixes with Premise (Sacchi et al., 2022). While this study provided deeper insight into material
64 and fossil fuel footprints for EoL treatment, the potential of ADR and HAS as a technology to produce
65 recycled sand and gravel and related environmental impacts has not been assessed.

66 Before the potential of recycling of EoL concrete and its environmental impacts can be assessed, we
67 first need to better understand the relationship between availability of EoL concrete and demand for
68 concrete. Additionally, it is not clear whether recycling concrete with ADR/HAS technologies may pose
69 any trade-offs with environmental impacts or how these recycled aggregates compare against
70 conventional aggregates in terms of their environmental impacts. In this study, we aim to address both

71 of these gaps. We develop a dynamic material flow analysis model (MFA) for global aggregates and
72 concrete to understand to what extent EoL concrete can provide secondary aggregates for future
73 concrete production in 26 regions of the world from 2025 to 2050. We then model the potential for and
74 environmental benefits of recycling concrete with ADR and HAS up to 2050. We do so by integrating
75 these technologies into a prospective version of the ecoinvent Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) database
76 (Wernet et al., 2016). We do this by linking the recycling processes to the sand and gravel markets,
77 letting all processes in the database that consume aggregates make use of the recycled aggregates as
78 well. We calculate potential environmental impacts using Premise to assess possible trade-offs from
79 recycling. Our method is further elaborated in section 2. Section 3 provides results and finally Section 4
80 gives the discussion and conclusions.

81

82 2. Methods

83 We start by developing a dynamic MFA model to assess the global potential of concrete recycling to
84 reduce the demand for conventional aggregates. Based on existing building material stock and flow data
85 from Deetman et al. (2020) we build a 'recycling material flow analysis model' to show how much
86 conventional aggregates could potentially be substituted by recycled aggregates in 26 global regions
87 from 2025 to up to 2050.

88 Next, we describe the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) goal and scope and the ADR/HAS inventories and
89 how we integrate them with Premise. We do this by linking the recycling processes to the sand and
90 gravel markets, letting all processes in the database that consume aggregates make use of the recycled
91 aggregates as well. After this, we assess the environmental impacts of the recycling technologies
92 compared to conventional production and assess what processes and products contribute to their
93 impacts.

94 Finally, we combine both the stock model data and the calculated environmental impacts to assess any
95 potential trade-offs at scale.

96 Our calculation of LCA results is done in Activity Browser 2.11.2 (Steubing et al., 2019) and the results
97 analysis done is with Excel (available as Supplementary Information (SI) 1). The python scripts for our
98 stock model and integration with ecoinvent data are provided as SI in van der Meide (2025).

99 2.1 Recycling material flow analysis model

100 To assess the availability of EoL concrete to recycle we make use of the outputs of Deetman et al.
101 (2020), who calculate in-and-outflow of concrete in the building stock for a given year and region
102 between 1970 and 2050. This is modeled with the IMAGE Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) (Stehfest et
103 al., 2014) for the SSP2 scenario (O'Neill et al., 2014), which projects likely policy changes based on
104 current and future policy plans. In this study, we only consider the recycling of concrete and use of
105 aggregates again in concrete as data for other aggregate uses (e.g. road-fill) is lacking.

106 We use the stock model outflow from Deetman et al. (2020) as available material for recycling and use
107 the inflow as demand for new concrete, we show this in Figure 1. We then split the EoL concrete outflow
108 from the building stock into production shares that ADR/HAS can produce. Based on the amount of
109 gravel/sand that can be produced from the outflow and the demand in a given year and region, we
110 calculate a balance. The balance for sand/gravel is zero, positive or negative for every timestep and
111 region. If the balance is zero, the demand can be satisfied exactly by the outflow of the concrete stock. If
112 the balance is positive (more material is available than is demanded), the remainder is considered to be
113 stored and available for future time steps in the same region. If the balance is negative (more material
114 is demanded than is available), the remainder can be supplied from the storage, any remainder after
115 that (e.g. when the storage is empty) must be produced as conventional concrete. Based on the balance,
116 the market share between conventional and recycled concrete is determined.

117 The amount of outflow from the building stock can also be moderated as not all material can realistically
118 be converted due to a recycled aggregates market that is still under-developed and other market/policy
119 inefficiencies. We assess two explorative scenarios from a stock model perspective:

- 120 - First, we assess a scenario where there would be no limit to market shares, i.e. everything that
121 can be recycled will be recycled. We name this scenario '*Maximum*'.
- 122 - Secondly, we assess a scenario where the market share of recycling increases over time, from
123 0% in 2025 to a maximum of 50% in 2050. We name this scenario '*up-to 50%*'.

124 We stress that both scenarios are meant as an exploration of the potential for recycling aggregates, and
125 do not reflect expectations with regards to market adoption of ADR and HAS. After assessing how much
126 sand and gravel can come from recycled sources –the substitution rate– in both scenarios, we will only

127 use the 'up-to 50%' scenario going further. We assess this scenario in more detail as it is the more
 128 realistic one of the two. We will show how much aggregates are produced from conventional and
 129 recycled sources in aggregated regions.

130
 131 *Figure 1. Recycling material flow analysis model. Starting from the top-middle, EoL concrete is partially*
 132 *recycled (amount depending on the scenario) and converted to recycled gravel by ADR and recycled*
 133 *sand by HAS. Depending on the demand for concrete (top left), gravel and sand are supplied, first by*
 134 *recycled sources and supplemented by conventional sources. The model is calculated from 2025-2050*
 135 *and the 26 IMAGE regions.*

136 2.2 Life Cycle Assessment

137 2.2.1 Goal and Scope

138 Our goal with the LCA is twofold: First, we want to compare environmental impacts between
 139 conventional and recycled aggregate production, and what contributes to those impacts. For this, we will
 140 assess a 'cradle-to-gate' production of aggregates. For the recycled aggregates, this means production
 141 from recycled EoL concrete. Secondly, we want to assess whether a shift to recycled aggregate
 142 production would pose any trade-offs compared to conventional aggregate production, which is why we
 143 combine it with Prospective LCA and our stock model to assess potential impacts up to 2050.

144 The scope of our assessment is the production of aggregates as described above, which will be
 145 integrated into a prospective version of the ecoinvent database (Wernet et al., 2016) using Premise
 146 (Sacchi et al., 2022). This integration means that other processes that require sand and gravel (e.g.
 147 concrete production) make use of both the conventional and recycled aggregates, immediately affecting
 148 all processes in the database that would make use of sand or gravel somewhere in their supply chains.
 149 Other database changes like the changes in the generation of electricity, transport and steel sector as
 150 made by Premise are also included. We assess the regionalized production of aggregates in all 26
 151 IMAGE regions, making use of the ecoinvent market mixes if multiple conventional production routes
 152 exist, to which we add the recycled shares from our stock model. The script to generate the prospective
 153 database is included as SI in van der Meide (2025).

154 For our assessment, we consider a functional unit of 'aggregates needed for 1 ton concrete', which is 373
 155 kg sand and 461 kg gravel, based on ecoinvent inventory data. We compare conventional and recycled
 156 aggregates to each other and compare the process contributions, grouped by product names, we apply a

157 cumulative cut-off of 80% to show the most important contributors, the full method is described by van
158 der Meide et al. (2025).

159 To keep this assessment in the context of the most important use of aggregates, concrete production for
160 this we use concrete production in Switzerland (in the IMAGE region Western Europe (WEU)). We show
161 the product contributions of sand, gravel and cement as described in van der Meide et al. (2025). For this
162 assessment, compare three alternatives: 100% conventional production in 2025, the market mix of 2050
163 with 20% recycled sand and 50% recycled gravel and a 100% recycled production.

164 Finally, based on the original LCA model and market shares between conventional and recycled
165 aggregates from our stock model we model, we assess how impacts change over time. We use the 'up-
166 to 50%' scenario to assess impacts. We assess impact of aggregate production in five year time steps
167 from 2025-2050 and show how the impacts change for the world average, highest and lowest regions on
168 a per-unit basis. Lastly, we combine the demand from the stock model and the per-unit impacts to
169 assess the potential total impact of aggregate production.

170 2.2.2 Advanced Dry Recovery (ADR) and Heated Air Classification System (HAS) Life Cycle 171 Inventory

172 For the LCA of recycled aggregates, we use updated inventories from Lotfi et al. (2017) for ADR and
173 Gebremariam et al. (2020) for HAS. We provide the exact inventories in the SI in van der Meide (2025)
174 but do discuss the technologies here from a Life Cycle Inventory perspective.

175 Advanced Dry Recovery (ADR) is meant to separate a stream of crushed end of life (EoL) concrete (0-
176 16mm) into two streams. One stream can be used to replace gravel and is 4-16mm in size and the other
177 is an intermediate of 0-4mm size that needs to be processed further. ADR works by physically
178 separating particles based on density (see also Lotfi et al. (2017)). The machine can be installed locally
179 on a deconstruction site, is filled and emptied by excavators and requires only electricity to run.

180 Heated Air Classification (HAS) is meant to separate the 0-4mm stream further into another two
181 streams. One stream can be used to replace sand and is 0.125-4mm in size and the other is 0-0.125mm.
182 In the future the latter stream may be used as a useful filler material in clinker, but we do not consider
183 this stream further in this study. HAS works by rapidly heating and cooling the particles, fracturing them
184 on weak points in their physical structure, splitting them into two stable fractions (as explained in more
185 detail by Gebremariam et al. (2020)). The machine can be installed locally on a deconstruction site, is
186 again filled and emptied by excavators and requires diesel to run. While Zhang et al. (2023) assessed the
187 potential for biodiesel use in HAS, we use conventional diesel in our inventory to make for a fairer
188 comparison to conventional aggregate production. We provide the ADR and HAS LCI in van der Meide
189 (2025).

190 We consider both ADR and HAS multifunctional processes, producing two sizes of recycled aggregates.
191 We apply mass-based allocation to the fractions, price-based allocation would not be possible as there
192 is no openly available pricing on aggregates globally nor for the ADR and HAS products. The mass
193 fractions of each stream are shown in Figure 1. We do not consider the processes as waste treatment
194 processes, this happens at an earlier step of concrete crushing, which happens for all waste treatment
195 options of EoL concrete, whether it is landfilled, used as road base or recycled with ADR and HAS. We
196 consider the crushing step cut-off for two reasons, this is consistent with the cut-off model from
197 ecoinvent (Wernet et al., 2016) and it is the same for all waste treatment options.

198 2.2.3 Conventional aggregates and concrete production Life Cycle Inventory

199 In our LCA we compare ADR and HAS to conventional production of aggregates, for this we use the
200 inventories available in ecoinvent:

- 201 • 'Gravel and Sand quarry operation' for 'sand' and 'gravel, round'

202 • 'Sand quarry operation, extraction from river bed' for 'sand'

203 • 'Zinc mine operation' for 'sand'

204 • 'Gravel production, crushed' for 'gravel, crushed'

205 Some regions have multiple processes available, while others have only one source available, e.g.
206 'India', which –according to the ecoinvent data- only produces sand from riverbed mining. We make use
207 of the market processes in ecoinvent so we use regional mixes for conventional production. For other
208 regions, we use the market shares from the global market in ecoinvent. While market shares between
209 these conventional routes could change, there currently is no information about these market shares
210 and we assume no change. The integration into the LCI database through Premise (Sacchi et al., 2022)
211 ensures that all consumers of aggregates in the database would consume from this modified market,
212 making use of both conventional and recycled sand and gravel where applicable. The market shares
213 between conventional and recycled aggregates differ per region and year based on our stock model.

214 2.2.4 Impact Assessment

215 We do a Life cycle impact assessment based on the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 impact categories
216 and characterization factors (EC, 2022). We focus on climate change, water use and land use, but
217 provide the results for all 25 impact categories in SI 1.

218

219 **3. Results**

220 **3.1 Stock model**

221 Our stock model shows how much sand and gravel can be substituted (indicated in percent relative to
222 the total demand in Figure 2). We modeled this for both the 'maximum' scenario without technological
223 limits to recycling and the 'up-to 50%' scenario where a maximum market share grows from 0% in 2025
224 to 50% in 2050.

225 In the maximum substitution scenario, we find that for sand the recycling depends mainly on the region
226 and does not grow over 60% for the highest region (Figure 2 A). For gravel, we find substantially higher
227 rates, even reaching a potential 100% substitution in some regions (Figure 2 B), suggesting that no
228 further production of conventional gravel would be necessary in those regions to produce concrete.

229 In the 'up-to 50%' scenario, we find a maximum rate of 29% in 2050 and most regions not passing 20%
230 (Figure 2 C). For gravel, we again find higher rates, though many regions still don't surpass the 40%
231 substitution (Figure 2 D).

232
233 **Figure 2. Substitution rate of recycled Aggregates over time. A: 'maximum' scenario for sand, B:**
234 **'maximum' scenario for gravel, C: 'up-to 50%' scenario for sand, D: 'up-to 50%' scenario for gravel**

235 For the 'up-to 50%' scenario we also show the aggregate demand for grouped regions (exact grouping
236 presented in SI 1) in Figure 3. In the figure, we show the total demand for aggregates for concrete
237 production in aggregated regions in five year steps and how much can be supplied from conventional
238 and recycled sources in 2050. We find that in 2050, 26% of global aggregate demand could come from
239 recycled sources, though about two thirds of this would be gravel.

240 Further, from Figure 3, we also find that demand in China is -and remains- the largest consumer of
241 aggregates. While this is not surprising, we also see a strong growth in the availability of EoL concrete.
242 In contrast, India also grows fast in total demand, but the end of life availability concrete remains
243 relatively low. This is due to the fact that China has been developing its housing and infrastructure
244 strongly for a longer period already, meaning that now already more stock reaches the end of life stage
245 and needs to be replaced, providing significant amounts of EoL concrete.

246

247 *Figure 3. Demand for aggregates, A: Demand in six aggregated regions between 2025-2050, B: Avoided*
 248 *production of conventional aggregates in the same regions of A in 2050 based on 50% scenario, C:*
 249 *Sources of sand and gravel in 2050 based on 50% scenario.*

250 **3.2 LCA ADR/HAS**

251 We assessed the environmental impacts for conventional and recycled aggregate production for 1 ton of
 252 concrete for the world average. We show comparative process contributions in Figure 4 A. We show the
 253 relative process contributions, grouped by product names for three important impact categories. The
 254 per-unit results for all 25 impact categories for sand, gravel and combined as aggregates are provided
 255 in SI 1. We find that for climate change impact, the 'diesel, burned' group results in a much higher impact
 256 for recycled aggregates, this is due to the HAS requiring substantial amounts of fuel. Furthermore, we
 257 find that for water use, over 80% of the impact can be explained directly by sand and gravel production
 258 for conventional production. While the per-unit impact for climate change is ~5x higher for recycled
 259 aggregates, the impacts in water use is ~4x lower and land use is ~20x lower.

260 To keep aggregates production in context of its main consumer, concrete production, we also assess the
 261 product contributions of sand, gravel and cement to concrete production in Switzerland based on the
 262 Central EU aggregates production, we do this for 100% conventional aggregates in 2025, the market mix
 263 of aggregates in 2050 (20% recycled sand, 50% recycled gravel, Figure 2) and 100% recycled aggregates
 264 in 2025. We show this in Figure 4 B. For the market mix of aggregates in 2050 compared to a 100%
 265 conventional production in 2025, we find that the contribution of aggregates to climate change increases
 266 from 2.8% to 5.3%. We find a < 1% decrease in water use impact and Land use contribution changes 3.7%.
 267 When assessing 100% recycled compared to re, the main changes are in the contribution of sand to
 268 climate change and reduction of the total land use of aggregates from 71.8% to only 14.2%.

269

270
 271 **Figure 4. Contributions to LCA results. A: Relative contributions of process groups to three major impact**
 272 **categories, cumulative to 80% of contributions. B: Product contributions to the production of 1m³**
 273 **concrete with 100% conventional aggregates, the 2050 mix of conventional/recycled aggregates and**
 274 **100% recycled aggregates for 'sand', 'gravel', 'cement' and all other products.**

275

276 **3.3 Prospective LCA**

277 With market shares between conventional and recycled aggregates known, environmental impacts per-
 278 unit can be calculated up to 2050. We show this for the 'up-to 50%' scenario in Figure 5. From this figure,
 279 we find a slightly increasing climate change impact, coinciding with increased market share of recycled
 280 aggregates. For water use, we find that 'Rest of South America' (RSAM) and India are outliers compared
 281 to the majority of the regions -5th to 95th percentile, between the error bars-, with most of the data
 282 slowly declining from ~7m³ to ~4m³. For land use, we find that India is again a major outlier, with most
 283 regions having much lower results. These outliers can be explained by regionalizedecoinvent market
 284 datasets that use only material from a single source. Finally, we find that per-unit of aggregates, China

285 shows the largest decline, due to its high recycling share. Overall, tradeoffs per unit of production for
 286 aggregates appear limited.

287
 288 Figure 5. Per-unit impact between 2025 and 2050 for aggregates, showing world average, the highest
 289 and lowest regions (labeled) and a 5th and 95th percentile as error bars. A: shows per-unit climate
 290 change impact, B: shows per-unit water use impact, C: shows per-unit land use impact, D: shows per-
 291 unit use of conventional aggregates.

292 Combining the per-unit impacts with the aggregate demand projected by the SSP2 scenario (as shown
 293 in Figure 3), we find that the total yearly climate change and land use impact from aggregates
 294 production would increase, while decreasing water use, as shown in Figure 6. Relating this back to
 295 concrete production, total land use could become a challenge, depending on the region.

296
 297 Figure 6. Impact of aggregate demand between 2025 and 2050 for aggregated regions. A: shows climate
 298 change impact, B: shows water use impact, C: shows land use impact.

299

300 4. Discussion

301 With our study, we have shown for the first time the potential of recycling aggregates from EoL concrete
302 in a future scenario with a stock model and how this would affect environmental impacts with
303 prospective LCA. We modeled the future potential of EoL concrete recycling to reduce sand and gravel
304 scarcity with a dynamic stock model. We coupled this data to a prospective LCA to assess potential
305 trade-offs of recycling with environmental impacts. From our assessment we found that up to 16% of
306 sand demand and 34% of gravel demand for concrete production could be substituted with sand and
307 gravel recycled from EoL concrete assuming a scenario where EoL concrete recycling reaches 50%
308 market share.

309 These relatively low substitution rates –especially for sand- can be explained by a combination of two
310 reasons: First, even if the ADR/HAS technologies would recycle all EoL concrete, the output is still only
311 19% recycled sand due to how ADR and HAS are currently used. This, combined with the fact that the
312 concrete types we assessed require 37%wt sand, means that not all sand could be from recycled
313 sources if the demand were the same as supply from EoL concrete. Secondly, many regions have a
314 mismatch between their demand for concrete and supply of EoL concrete. If more material is required
315 for new construction than becomes available for recycling, not all material can be recycled by definition
316 –a circularity gap (Krausmann et al., 2017)-, we see this back in our comparison between the China and
317 India regions in Figure 3.

318 While this circularity gap between demand for new concrete and supply from EoL concrete cannot be
319 closed entirely, it can help significantly reduce demand for conventional sand and gravel. Recycling can
320 especially help in regions where there is low growth, while regions like India and Africa would still need
321 to supply a major share of their production from conventional sources.

322 In terms of environmental trade-offs with increases in supply from conventional sources, impacts can
323 be expected to increase, though in the context of environmental impacts of concrete production, the
324 increase would be rather limited. Specifically for climate change, the contribution of sand and gravel to
325 concrete production would still only account for <5% if the total impact, with the majority of the impact
326 still caused by clinker production. Despite this, ADR and HAS still have a high energy cost, making the
327 cost-effectiveness of HAS largely dependent on the cost of energy. Technology developers should
328 attempt to improve this in the future.

329 One major challenge for the production of sand and gravel is that the production is often limited to local
330 production and consumption –though exceptions like Singapore exist, which imports significant amounts
331 of sand (Peduzzi, 2014)-. The low value of sand and gravel per unit weight makes it often uneconomical to
332 transport over large distances, making scarcity of sand and gravel a local problem, requiring local
333 solutions. We represented this in our model by only considering the balance between EoL concrete
334 availability and consumption per region.

335 A main problem with recycling is that it can only partially help resolving current scarcity issues. It helps
336 to reduce demand for conventional sand and gravel, but due to a still rising demand for concrete in
337 many regions and imperfect collection and recycling, recycled aggregates can cover the needs for
338 aggregates only for 26% (Figure 6). Recycling must be combined with other measures like reducing
339 demand for aggregates e.g. like Zhong et al. (2022) modeled. Specifically for regions that have had
340 strong growth in the past, this may be effective now, as there would still be a major amount of stock
341 from the built environment, reducing the circularity gap in the future. For regions that do currently not
342 have a large stock of materials in the built environment, this would not help reduce the circularity gap
343 much as the ratio of demand and availability of EoL sand and gravel would not change much.

344 We identify one main limitation to our study: We modeled ADR and HAS while there are more
345 technologies to recycled EoL concrete (Ren et al., 2021; Y. Zhang et al., 2019). We used ADR and HAS due
346 to availability of data and it's promising cost-effectiveness and market readiness. Our stock model can

347 be adjusted with different recycling parameters and the Life Cycle Inventories could also be changed to
348 apply our models to different technologies to assess their potential.

349 While we assess the potential to reduce sand and gravel demand and its associated environmental
350 impacts, we do not know how these values relate to actual aggregate availability and scarcity problems,
351 this would be a topic that needs to be investigated in the future. This needs to be studied both a level of
352 local impact, but also globally.

353

354

355 **Declaration of Interests and funding**

356 This study has been partially funded by the ICEBERG project, which is financed by the European Union
357 H2020 programme (grant no. 869336). The ADR and HAS technologies are partially developed by the
358 company C2CA, which also took part in the ICEBERG project. Neither the funders nor technology
359 developers had a role in study design, data analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the
360 manuscript. Data was provided by C2CA during the project.

361 **CRedit author statement**

362 Marc van der Meide: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft,
363 Visualization

364 Mingming Hu: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

365 Arnold Tukker: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

366 Berhard Steubing: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

367

368

369

370 **References**

- 371 Cao, Z., & Masanet, E. (2022). Material efficiency to tackle the sand crisis. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(5),
372 370–371. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00869-w>
- 373 Deetman, S., Marinova, S., Van Der Voet, E., Van Vuuren, D. P., Edelenbosch, O., & Heijungs, R. (2020).
374 Modelling global material stocks and flows for residential and service sector buildings towards
375 2050. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 245, 118658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118658>
- 376 EC. (2022). *Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1* [Dataset].
377 <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/LCDN/developerEF.html>
- 378 Gebremariam, A. T., Di Maio, F., Vahidi, A., & Rem, P. (2020). Innovative technologies for recycling End-of-
379 Life concrete waste in the built environment. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 163, 104911.
380 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104911>
- 381 Giljum, S., Hinterberger, F., Bruckner, M., Burger, E., Fruhmann, J., Lutter, S., Pirgmaier, E., Polzin, C.,
382 Waxwender, H., Kernegger, L., & Warhust, M. (2000). *Overconsumption? Our use of the world's*
383 *natural resources*. SERI. <https://dl.icdst.org/pdfs/files2/263d94705b1db13330192f3a57d693f7.pdf>
- 384 Ioannidou, D., Meylan, G., Sonnemann, G., & Habert, G. (2017). Is gravel becoming scarce? Evaluating the
385 local criticality of construction aggregates. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 126, 25–33.
386 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.07.016>
- 387 Krausmann, F., Wiedenhofer, D., Lauk, C., Haas, W., Tanikawa, H., Fishman, T., Miatto, A., Schandl, H., &
388 Haberl, H. (2017). Global socioeconomic material stocks rise 23-fold over the 20th century and
389 require half of annual resource use. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(8),
390 1880–1885. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1613773114>
- 391 Lotfi, S., Rem, P., Deja, J., & Mróz, R. (2017). An experimental study on the relation between input
392 variables and output quality of a new concrete recycling process. *Construction and Building*
393 *Materials*, 137, 128–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.01.085>

394 Müller, A., Harpprecht, C., Sacchi, R., Maes, B., Van Sluisveld, M., Daioglou, V., Šavija, B., & Steubing, B.
395 (2024). Decarbonizing the cement industry: Findings from coupling prospective life cycle
396 assessment of clinker with integrated assessment model scenarios. *Journal of Cleaner
397 Production*, 450, 141884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141884>

398 O'Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Ebi, K. L., Hallegatte, S., Carter, T. R., Mathur, R., & van Vuuren, D. P.
399 (2014). A new scenario framework for climate change research: The concept of shared
400 socioeconomic pathways. *Climatic Change*, 122(3), 387–400. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-
401 0905-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-
401 0905-2)

402 Peduzzi, P. (2014). Sand, rarer than one thinks. *Environmental Development*, 11, 208–218.
403 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2014.04.001>

404 Ren, P., Ling, T.-C., & Mo, K. H. (2021). Recent advances in artificial aggregate production. *Journal of
405 Cleaner Production*, 291, 125215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125215>

406 Sacchi, R., Terlouw, T., Siala, K., Dirnaichner, A., Bauer, C., Cox, B., Mutel, C., Daioglou, V., & Luderer, G.
407 (2022). PRospective EnvironMental Impact asSEment (premise): A streamlined approach to
408 producing databases for prospective life cycle assessment using integrated assessment
409 models. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 160, 112311.
410 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112311>

411 Stehfest, E., van Vuuren, D. P., Kram, T., Bouwman, L., Alkemade, R., Bakkenes, M., Biemans, H.,
412 Bouwman, A., Elzen, M., Janse, J., Lucas, P., van Minnen, J., Muller, C., & Prins, A. G. (2014).
413 *Integrated Assessment of Global Environmental Change with IMAGE 3.0. Model description and
414 policy applications*. PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.
415 [https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/integrated-assessment-of-global-environmental-change-
416 with-IMAGE-3.0](https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/integrated-assessment-of-global-environmental-change-
416 with-IMAGE-3.0)

417 Steubing, B., Koning, Haas, & Mutel, C. (2019). The Activity Browser – An open source LCA software
418 building on top of the brightway framework. *Software Impacts*, 100012.
419 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2019.100012>

420 Sverdrup, H. U., Koca, D., & Schlyter, P. (2017). A Simple System Dynamics Model for the Global
421 Production Rate of Sand, Gravel, Crushed Rock and Stone, Market Prices and Long-Term Supply
422 Embedded into the WORLD6 Model. *BioPhysical Economics and Resource Quality*, 2(2), 8.
423 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41247-017-0023-2>

424 Torres, A., Brandt, J., Lear, K., & Liu, J. (2017). A looming tragedy of the sand commons. *Science*,
425 357(6355), 970–971. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao0503>

426 Tukker, A., Behrens, P., Deetman, S., Hu, M., Alejandre, E. M., van der Meide, M., Zhong, X., & Zhang, C.
427 (2023). Circular construction: Six key recommendations. *One Earth*, 6(11), 1425–1429.
428 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.10.021>

429 Van Der Meide, M. (2025). *Data for: Recovering sand and gravel from End-of-Life concrete: The global*
430 *potential* [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15304338>

431 van der Meide, M., Harpprecht, C., Northey, S., Yongxiang, Y., & Steubing, B. (2022). Effects of the energy
432 transition on environmental impacts of cobalt supply: A prospective life cycle assessment study
433 on future supply of cobalt. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13258>

434 Van Der Meide, M., Heijungs, R., Guinée, J., Hu, M., & Steubing, B. (2025). *Contribution Analysis in LCA: an*
435 *overview of approaches and when to apply them*. OSF Preprints.
436 https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/sfgj6_v1

437 Watari, T., Cao, Z., Serrenho, A. C., & Cullen, J. (2023). Growing role of concrete in sand and climate
438 crises. *iScience*, 26(5), 106782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.106782>

439 Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., & Weidema, B. (2016). The ecoinvent
440 database version 3 (part I): Overview and methodology. *The International Journal of Life Cycle*
441 *Assessment*, 21(9), 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>

442 Zhang, C., Hu, M., Di Maio, F., Sprecher, B., Yang, X., & Tukker, A. (2022). An overview of the waste
443 hierarchy framework for analyzing the circularity in construction and demolition waste
444 management in Europe. *Science of The Total Environment*, 803, 149892.
445 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149892>

446 Zhang, C., Hu, M., van der Meide, M., Di Maio, F., Yang, X., Gao, X., Li, K., Zhao, H., & Li, C. (2023). Life cycle
447 assessment of material footprint in recycling: A case of concrete recycling. *Waste Management*,
448 155, 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2022.10.035>

449 Zhang, Y., Luo, W., Wang, J., Wang, Y., Xu, Y., & Xiao, J. (2019). A review of life cycle assessment of
450 recycled aggregate concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 209, 115–125.
451 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.03.078>

452 Zhong, X., Deetman, S., Tukker, A., & Behrens, P. (2022). Increasing material efficiencies of buildings to
453 address the global sand crisis. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(5), 389–392.
454 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00857-0>

455